

Gender differences in happiness in association to cognitive flexibility among adults: An exploratory study

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Happiness is one of the important aspects of an adult's life in terms of health, productivity, and general well-being. Happiness is defined as 'people's evaluations of their lives and encompasses both cognitive judgements of satisfaction and affective appraisals of mood and emotions (Diener et al., 2008). There are gender differences in levels of happiness across cultures. Various factors determine happiness; one of them is cognitive flexibility, i.e., the ability to shift perspectives to adapt to changes in the environment. High cognitive flexibility has been associated with psychological well-being and effective coping, whereas low flexibility, or rigidity, has been linked to several types of psychopathology. Studies indicate that enhanced happiness increases cognitive flexibility (Wang et al., 2017). In this light, the present study explores the gender differences in happiness and cognitive flexibility between males and females. Secondly, the study also examines whether cognitive flexibility is associated with happiness. Participants of both genders ($N=60$) were taken as per inclusion criterion, and Oxford Happiness Questionnaire (OHQ) was used to assess the personal level of happiness, and Stroop Test and Trail Making Test (TMT-II) were administered to assess cognitive flexibility. Results indicate the association between cognitive flexibility and happiness. Implications of the study focus on the role of cognitive flexibility as a tool to enhance happiness.

Keywords: cognitive flexibility; gender; happiness; psychopathology; well-being

Happiness is a highly valued component in present-day society. People aim at happiness in their own lives and also care for the happiness of other people. This classic philosophy is not only more accepted these days but even more practicable, owing to many recent views provided by scientific research on the conditions for happiness (Veenhoven, 2004). In a broad sense, the word happiness is often synonymously used with 'quality of life' or 'well-being'. However, the meaning denotes that life is good but does not specify what is good about life. These four qualities include liveability of the environment, life-ability of the person, the utility of life, and satisfaction.

In 1973, 'Psychology Abstracts International' began listing happiness as an index term (Diener, 1984). Happiness is the degree to which an individual judge the overall quality of their life-as-a-whole favourably. In other words: how much one likes the life one leads. However, because happiness is a term used widely and frequently, it has various meanings and connotations (Diener, 1984). The construct of happiness is still evolving and a construct that can be empirically evaluated through qualitative and quantitative assessment (Delle Fave et al., 2011). Delle Fave and colleagues (2011) noted that happiness is also an ambiguous term that can have several meanings: (a) A transient emotion (that is synonymous with joy); (b) an experience of fulfilment and accomplishment (characterised by a cognitive evaluation); and (c) long-term process of meaning-making and identity development through achieving one's potential and the pursuit of subjectively relevant goals.

The word 'happiness' is based on three kinds of appraisal: the overall judgement of favourableness described above, and these two other specific appraisals. These specific appraisals are seen as 'components' of happiness. The components are referred to as 'hedonic level of affect' i.e., the degree to which various affects that someone experiences are pleasant in character, and 'contentment' i.e., the degree to which an individual perceives their aspirations are met.

Historically, since the days of Aristotle, happiness was conceptualised as being comprised of at least two aspects – *hedonia* (or pleasure) and *eudaimonia* (a sense that life is well-lived) (Kringelbach & Berridge, 2010). Moving forward into the modern era, there have been many other perspectives that makeup theories of happiness. The Affective State Theory of Happiness proposed that happiness is the result of one's overall emotional state. Bradburn (1969) argues that happiness is made up of two separate components that are quite independent and uncorrelated: positive affect and negative affect. On the other hand, cognitive theories held that happiness is a product of human thinking and reflects discrepancies between perceptions of life-as-it-is and notions of how-life-should-be. Notions of how life should be are assumed to be rooted in collective beliefs and to vary across cultures. The construct of happiness is still evolving, and many more perspectives will add to the present viewpoint.

Generally, gender has been considered one of the weak predictors of happiness (Diener et al. 1999; Hunter & Csikszentmihalyi, 2003), and studies have yielded mixed results. Previous studies reveal that gender is related to subjective well-being and that women tended to report higher happiness than men (Zweig, 2014). Also, Tkach and Lyubomirsky (2006) found that even though men and women are equally happy, gender differences were found in the use of happiness-enhancing strategies.

Even if gender has no direct association with happiness, this does not rule out the possibility that gender might condition the effect of other variables which affect the process of subjective well-being formation is different between males and females. One such variable which determines happiness and may differ in males and females is that of cognitive flexibility. Studies suggest that cognitive differences are evident between men and women (Croese et al., 1992; Van Eeden et al., 2000). Cognitive flexibility is the human ability to adapt cognitive processing strategies to face new and unexpected conditions in the environment (Cañas et al., 2005). The generation of appropriate action depends on the ability to select suitable responses among other competing responses, thereby inhibiting the irrelevant responses. These abilities are generally called 'cognitive flexibility' (Rende, 2000). Studies of cognitive flexibility have been investigated with diverse cognitive tasks, including task switching (Druey, 2014; Woodward et al., 2002;), attention shifting (Wager et al., 2004), and so on. Cognitive flexibility is important for creativity, learning when reward contingencies change, and redirecting our attention (Relajo-Howell, 2020).

Along these lines, one of the important cognitive theories, i.e., the Broaden and Build Theory, suggests that rather than fuelling specific action tendencies, positive emotions appear to spark broadened and expansive thought-action tendencies. They affect our thoughts and attention, thereby leading to broadened and expansive attention. Also, positive emotions enhance flexibility and creative thinking, and problem-solving (Relajo et al., 2015). These together accumulate and build psychological, physical, and social resources for individuals in the long run. (Fredrickson, 1998, 2001, 2004).

Recent studies have shown that positive emotion enhances cognitive flexibility. Many studies exhibited that positive emotion reduced response conflict and suppressed competing response (Van der Stigchel et al., 2011). For example, in a Simon or Flanker task, a significant conflict effect was observed in neutral trials, but not in positive trials (Kanske and Kotz, 2011a,b; Xue et al., 2013), indicating that positive emotion reduced response to conflict. Nadler et al. (2010) examined the effect of mood states on cognitive processing by means of a category learning task where participants were asked to classify stimuli by rule-described categories. Music and video clips were used to induce a happy or sad mood. Results indicated that the performance in the happy mood was better than that in the sad mood.

However, there have also been studies that indicate contradictory findings. Studies have indicated positive emotions impair the switching of attention to stimuli that were previously ignored (e.g., Dreisbach & Goschke, 2004). Also, happiness impairs performance in a switching Stroop task (Phillips et al., 2002).

Current studies of gender differences related to happiness and psychological well-being reflect contradictory results and a distinct lack of consensus. Males and females differ in terms of happiness, suggesting that gender might have an effect on cognitive flexibility in relation to happiness. Also, there are major inconsistencies in empirical findings regarding the association between positive emotions or happiness and cognitive flexibility. Inconsistencies may be due to the variability of tasks used in previous studies to measure cognitive flexibility. Also, most studies have studied cognitive flexibility in relation to induced emotions: positive or negative in laboratory situations. Thus, inconsistencies in results might rise as a result of the transitory effect of the emotion. This may have a different effect in comparison to the pervasive level of happiness the individual experiences at a point in time. Considering these potentialities, in the present study, more than one measure of cognitive flexibility has been used with respect to happiness. Thus, the present study primarily aims to study the differences in measures of happiness and cognitive flexibility between males and females. The secondary aim of the study is to explore the association between cognitive flexibility and happiness and how cognitive flexibility affects happiness in both genders.

METHODS

Sample

Participants of both sexes ($N = 60$) between the ages of 18–55 participated in the study. The sample consisted of 30 males (Mean age = 30.6 years, $SD = 8.8$) and 30 females (Mean age = 30.87, $SD = 11.54$). Participants recruited had a formal education at least till class X. Individuals suffering from any chronic physical illness or any other psychiatric illness were excluded from the study.

Instruments

An information schedule is covering information on age, sex, education, occupation, information on physical and mental illness (if any), several aspects of happiness.

Oxford Happiness Questionnaire. The Oxford Happiness Questionnaire (OHQ) was devised by Hills and Argyle (2002), is a 29- self-report questionnaire that employs a 6-point Likert scale response format from strongly disagree = 1, to strongly agree = 6; with the higher scores corresponding to higher levels of happiness. It contains 12 negatively worded items that require reverse coding before calculating the total happiness score, which is a sum of individual item scores. The OHQ has a good internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha at the level of 0.90 and above. (Hills & Argyle, 2002)

Stroop Test. The Stroop Test (NIMHANS version) was used to assess cognitive flexibility. The colour names 'blue', 'green', 'red', and 'yellow' were printed in capital letters on a paper, and the colour of the words occasionally correspond to the colour designated by the word. The words are printed in 16 rows and 11 columns. The time taken for reading the words column-wise is first noted, followed by the time taken to read the colour the word is printed in, again column-wise. The Stroop Effect is calculated by subtracting the word reading time from the colour reading time (converted to seconds).

Trail Making Test. The Trail Making Test (TMT) is a brief paper and neuropsychological pencil test of visual attention and task switching. In the present study, the Trail Making Test was used to assess cognitive flexibility. It consists of two parts, A and B. Errors were pointed out by the examiner as they occur so that the participant can complete the test without errors. The score is only based on the time taken. In general, performance is

considered impaired if scores exceed 40 seconds for part A and 91 seconds for part B. The total time taken to complete the task was considered as the final score. Several errors were not recorded.

Procedure

Participants gave written informed consent and were assured that the individual identity would be kept confidential. They then completed a brief demographic questionnaire. Participants were tested individually for 20 min, and tests were administered in the following fixed order: Oxford Happiness Questionnaire, Stroop Test, and then the Trail Making Test. Complete administration was done in a single session. Necessary precautions were taken so that participants understood the instructions clearly and no questions were left out. Scoring was done by following the respective scoring procedure for each test.

RESULTS

Socio-demographic data (Table 1) reveal the majority of the sample were graduates, both males and females. The mean age for males is 30.6 years and females is 30.87 years respectively. More than half of the sample was unmarried. Most of the female subjects were students. Owing to the time constraint, it was not possible to include more participants.

Table 1
 Sociodemographic details of the participants

Domains		Males		Females	
Age		$M \pm SD = 30.6 \pm 8.8$		$M \pm SD = 30.87 \pm 11.54$	
		<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
Religion	Christian	1	3.00	0	0
	Hindu	24	80	30	100
	Muslim	4	13.34	0	0
	Sikh				
Education	12 Years	3	10	2	6.67
	12 + 3	16	53.33	15	50
	12 + 5	11	36.67	13	43.33
Marital status	Married	11	36.67	11	36.67
	Unmarried	19	63.33	19	63.33
Occupation	Employed	16	53.33	9	30
	Student	14	46.67	21	70

Table 2 shows means and standard deviations for all measures in males and females. No significant difference has been found between males and females with respect to happiness and cognitive flexibility. However, females have higher means in happiness as compared to males and lower means in both measures of cognitive flexibility.

Table 2
 Mean and standard deviation across three variables

Variables	Gender	<i>M</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Happiness	Female	4.30 ± 0.55	0.47	0.640
	Male	4.23 ± 0.59		

Trail Making Test	Female	74 ± 28.72	0.78	0.438
	Male	67.64 ± 34.6		
Stroop Test	Female	6.63 ± 5.61	1.32	0.192
	Male	5.033 ± 3.54		

Table 3 suggests no significant correlation between happiness and cognitive flexibility in the total sample. However, it can be seen that in adults, happiness and performance on TMT has a low negative correlation. In case of males, results indicate a low negative correlation between happiness and performance on TMT and in case of females a negative correlation exists between happiness and performance on Stroop Test.

Correlation B/W	Total (N= 30)		Female (N= 30)		Male (N= 30)	
	CE	<i>p</i>	CE	<i>p</i>	CE	<i>p</i>
Happiness and TMT	-0.14	0.460	0.19	0.497	-0.184	0.511
Happiness and Stroop	0.12	0.527	-0.45	-0.45	0.07	0.804

DISCUSSION

Perception of happiness differs across gender and is related to cognitive flexibility, which is one of the important factors that determine happiness. High cognitive flexibility has been associated with psychological well-being and effective coping, whereas low flexibility, or rigidity, has been linked to several types of psychopathology. It is well recognised that positive affect leads to greater cognitive flexibility. (Ashby et al., 1999).

The present study did not show any significant differences in measures of happiness between males and females owing to the small sample size and inadequate representation of the population. However, comparing the means has shown that females have higher means of happiness than males and lower means in both cognitive flexibility measures. Males perceive themselves to display greater flexibility in thought which is appropriate to the context, and they focus on problem-solving rather than making value judgements. This suggests the ability to emotionally distance oneself from the context and concentrate on practical elements in a goal-directed manner. This finding may also be reflected in the lower level of happiness obtained by the males in this study. Also, happiness is associated with pleasantness, certainty, and perceived control (Smith & Ellsworth, 1985). Thus, individuals already having a sense of control may not feel the need to establish control, thereby reducing performance in tasks of cognitive flexibility, which has been seen in case of females in the present study.

Findings from the present study have also not found any overall significant association between happiness and cognitive flexibility. However, they suggest an association might exist between happiness and cognitive flexibility. Flexibility is not a unitary concept and whether happiness improves flexibility tends to depend on the type of flexibility. The present study's findings align with research that suggests that happiness can impair cognitive flexibility in switching tasks such as the Stroop Test (Philips et al., 2002).

The study had several limitations, however. Considering the time constraint, the sample size was small and may not be the very true representation of the population. Also, the participants were mostly drawn from urban localities in Kolkata and had a fair educational background. Taking participants from diverse backgrounds could have given better scope for exploration. Future studies can be done involving a larger sample from diverse backgrounds and segregating the different components of happiness and cognitive flexibility.

CONCLUSION

Among several determinants of happiness, cognitive flexibility is a major one. More precisely, both happiness and cognitive flexibility seem to have mutual influence on each other. Adapting flexibly to our daily environment enhances our happiness and well-being. Regulating ourselves in new and unexpected conditions is an important key to happiness. Thus, cognitive flexibility does influence the perception of happiness in individuals. Interestingly, we can also see that depending on the situational context as well as task in hand,

happiness can enhance one's flexibility or may also impair it. The present study also put forwards that happiness and cognitive flexibility may be associated. However, it becomes important to consider happiness in terms of the type of flexibility involved in a particular situation, and not just cognitive flexibility as a unitary concept.

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